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The Problems Faced by Refugee Students in The Education Process

Salih Alpaslan Sekin¹, Rahman Çakir²

¹ Bahçeşehir College, Şanlıurfa, Turkey. ORCID: 0000-0002-8810-559X

² Giresun University, Giresun, Turkey. ORCID: 0000-0003-1752-3855

Correspondence: Rahman Çakir, Giresun University, Faculty of Education, Giresun, Turkey.
E-mail: rahmancakir@hotmail.com

Abstract

This study aims to investigate the problems faced by refugee students during the education process. This research was conducted in qualitative research model and phenomenology pattern. An interview form was used to determine the opinions of students, parents, teachers and administrators. The study group of the research consists of 18 refugee students in 11 primary schools in Osmaniye Province in 2017-2018 academic year, 18 parents of refugee students, 26 teachers and 21 school administrators. The study group was determined by the criterion sampling method. Descriptive analysis was used in the data analysis. Expert opinion was used to ensure content validity reliability of data collection tool. It was observed that students experienced aggressive behavior, exclusion, communication and adaptation problems. Perceptions of teachers and administrators about refugee students in their institutions are positive. They support each other in problems with refugee students. Students and parents receive support from teachers and administrators in case of problems.

Keywords: Refugee Student, Primary School, Problems, Parent, Teacher, Administrator

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. The Concept of Immigration

Defined as the most fundamental element of society, human beings are not content with what they have, and strive for more and better (Ağaoğlu, 2013). Making an effective definition of migration requires knowledge on the place, cause, duration and direction of migration (Coşkun & Yolcu, 2016). When migration is examined, we come across the idea of people changing their positions in order to reach a better standard than their current situation. Although most of the migrations in the world are based on such reasons as life safety, it is an undeniable fact that there are migrations made to reach more or the better.

Throughout history, migrations have been a phenomenon that shaped societies in social, economic and cultural terms. Today, major migration movements are taking place as people escape from civil war for safety reasons,

leaving all their wealth in their country (Harunoğulları, 2016). As a result of mass migration, citizens of the countries receiving immigration and immigrants themselves face great problems. (Sezgin & Yolcu, 2016).

1.2. The Problems of Refugees in the World

According to Measham et al. (2014), immigrants face many problems after migration. The problem of adaptation to the society they migrated to, states causing difficulties in accessing social services, exclusion from social life and discrimination, difficulty in speaking the language of the migrated society, children not being able to have education are some of the problems faced by immigrants (as cited by Mercan-Uzun and Bütün, 2016). Social adaptation problems are at the top of the problems experienced by refugees worldwide (Kızıl & Dönmez, 2017).

According to Cesariye (2006), refugees experience serious psychological trauma. While hoping to return to their countries when the conflicts in their countries are over, many are uncertain about what will happen in the future. The dilemma caused by this uncertainty not only delays the refugees setting their lives in order in the host country but also slows down social harmony and assimilation. As a result of the major changes in the lives of refugees in the wake of migration, an increase is observed in the number of children who quit their education for economic reasons and start working life (Harunoğulları, 2016).

The increasing in immigration in recent years has convinced states that the necessity of integration should be taken into account. They attached importance to education as their strongest weapon in the face of this fear. In social sciences research, while individuals who come to the host country as a child or at a young age and receive some or all of the schooling process in the new society are called generation 1.5, the individuals born in the host society and receive education services in the society where their family is an immigrant are called the second generation. About a quarter of young people in the Netherlands, Sweden and the USA, and one-sixth of the young in France and England constitute the generations 1.5 and 2nd (Alba and Holdaway, 2017).

Many studies in the literature have shown that countries approach developing educational policies regarding refugee education reactively. The underlying reason for the reactive approach is that socially advantageous individuals want to give advantage to the children of their own society, especially their own children. As consequence of all these efforts, inequality in education is increasing. This makes it difficult for refugee children to become a part of society in the future. Since education continues at home and in the society after school, refugee parents who do not know the language of the host country are not able to deal with their children's education life adequately. This situation delays refugee students from overcoming the language problem. One of the practices that yielded positive results regarding the solution of this problem is to increase the extra time spent by the refugee student at school. In this way, the student has extra opportunities and possibilities to reduce his/her disadvantage. Another practice is to prevent communication problems by communicating with the help of a translator in contact meetings so that the family is more involved in the education process. Schools attended by refugee students are in many ways poorer quality schools than children of middle-class families. This means that refugee students are negatively affected by inequalities in schools. Among these qualifications are school funding, teachers' skills and classroom environment.

1.3. The Circumstances of Refugees in Turkey

Republic of Turkey, based on its geographical location and its experiences throughout history, consider those coming from outside of Europe as people who are to migrate to Europe. Therefore, it signed the Geneva Convention on the Legal Status of Refugees, signed in 1951, but placed a geographical limitation. According to the said geographical limitation, the Republic of Turkey only accepts those coming from European countries as refugees. Turkey's functioning as a bridge between East and West due to its geographical location has caused it to be a country where the discriminating between refugees is actively done (Aykut, 2016). Syria's neighboring countries, particularly Turkey, which hosts the greatest migration movement of recent years, do their duties imposed by international law and humanity in the best manner (Kızıl and Dönmez, 2017). As a result of the instability and civil war in Syria, many Syrians have immigrated to other countries. From the start of the events in 2011, the State of the Republic of Turkey has been the country that accepted the most of the asylum seekers

(Harunoğulları, 2011). According to immigrant behavior, Anatolia is just a transit route. Republic of Turkey, based on its geographical location and its experiences throughout history, consider those coming from outside of Europe as people who are to migrate to Europe. Therefore, it signed the Geneva Convention on the Legal Status of Refugees, signed in 1951, but placed a geographical limitation. According to the said geographical limitation, the Republic of Turkey only accepts those coming from European countries as refugees. Turkey's functioning as a bridge between East and West due to its geographical location has caused it to be a country where the discrimination between refugees is actively practiced (Aykut, 2016).

Even though the determination of the actual number is impossible due to various reasons, according to the data of many official institutions, such as Coast Guard Command and Directorate General of Migration Management, Syrians constitute the largest proportion of asylum seekers in Turkey (Aykut, 2016). Republic of Turkey carrying out the open door policy for those fleeing from the war in Syria and illegal crossings taking place apart from not being able to keep an account of refugees accurately have caused inability to know the exact number of Syrian refugees in our country (Mercan, Uzun and Bütün, 2016). There are no certain data obtained or a comprehensive report on Syrians living outside the camps in Turkey (Aykut, 2016). Despite this, asylum seekers were provided with residence permits, health services, education services and job opportunities, so that they adapt to their new lives and gain their self-confidence (Yıldız, 2013).

The educational planning of Syrian migrants, based on the assumption that they will return to their countries in a short time as a result of the end of civil war, has been changed many times with the prolongation of the refugees' visiting time (Kızıllı & Dönmez, 2017). In order to alleviate difficulties caused by civil war and immigration Syrian refugees experience, Republic of Turkey, by means of Turkish Red Crescent, meet their social needs like psychological therapy in addition to their basic needs such as food and shelter (Aykut, 2016). The most important source of motivation for Syrian refugees in the social adaptation and acceptance process is that they are provided with the access to educational activities (Sezgin & Yolcu, 2016). Because it is assumed that education will enable young people to gain cultural flexibility and increase their adaptation to the conditions they live in due to the constant change of cultural structure and values (Güven, 2011). As a result of international agreements and migrations, cross-cultural interaction is assumed. Changing the way states define the concept of citizenship, it paved the way for multicultural education studies (Cırık, 2008). The general purposes of Turkish national education have been arranged to cover all members of the society, and it has been clearly stated that every individual has the right to education, that they can benefit from this right, educational opportunities and equality of opportunity in education (Gül, 2018). 'All members of the society without any distinction of origin' is emphasized.

In international agreements, the right to education is one of the most fundamental rights of refugees (Kızıllı & Dönmez, 2017). The principle of universality and equality is one of the basic principles of Turkish National Education. According to this principle, no discrimination can be done in educational institutions in terms of language, race, gender and religion. Everyone benefits from educational institutions and educational rights equally. No privilege is given to anyone, any group or any class in educational services (Konan, 2002).

Taking care of the needs of the individual and society is another of the basic principles of national education. National education services designed according to the demands, expectations and needs of the society also take into account the capabilities of the citizens (Konan, 2002). Although the asylum seekers are not citizens, the fact that most of them acquire citizenship in the following years and this expectation is high in our country should be taken into account in academic studies on asylum seekers. Besides, the adaptation of asylum seekers to the society is a need of both the asylum seekers and Turkish citizens. The way to meet this need of the individual and society is through education. Based on this premise, the problems that may be encountered in the future should be anticipated today and necessary education services should be provided to refugee children in order to meet the needs of the individual and the society to eliminate these problems.

1.4. The Problem of the Research

Migration has a structure that includes many economic, social, psychological and cultural problems (Sağlam, 2006). One of the most important reasons for migration is that immigrants leave their country with their relatives in order to achieve a quality life (Lordoğlu, 2015). Republic of Turkey is located on the transition routes of three continents. Since it is located on these transit routes, it contains many different immigrant communities within itself (Yılmaz, 2014). Turkey has become a country with rapidly growing immigrant population after the second millennium (Topçuoğlu, 2014).

Although developed countries seem to be taking responsibility for the refugee and asylum problem, the main burden is imposed on developing countries. As with many countries, the phenomenon of migration affects the Republic of Turkey's socio-cultural, economic and demographic structure. In addition, it creates problems in public order and security. (Directorate General of Migration Management, 2017).

As a result of the civil war in Syria, a large migration movement towards Turkey took place (GNAT Human Rights Inquiry Committee, 2014). At the end of this civil war, at least 400 thousand people, including children and civilians, lost their lives. 13.5 million people, more than half of the 20 million Syrian population, got in need of the help of other countries. More than 6 million people had to emigrate from their homeland. 4.8 million people that are the majority of these people took refuge in neighboring countries, primarily the state of Turkey. (DEMP, 2017). According to the authorities of the Republic of Turkey, in the course of time, these events once seen as a temporary situation have become a problem that cannot be solved for many years. Since 2011, millions of Syrians have involved in the social life in Turkey, got into the working life and made efforts to get their lives in order in Turkey. According to the data of 2016, in foreigners with residence permits in Turkey, Syrians rank first with 48.738 people. Again, according to the data of 2016, it is seen that most of the irregular migrants apprehended were Syrians with 69,755 people (DGMM, 2017). Besides that, it is a prevailing opinion that apart from Syrians who fled from the war and came to Turkey as refugees the number of the ones who came illegally is much higher than the registered ones (Boyras, 2015). It is believed that about half of the number of Syrian refugees are in Turkey (Göker and Keskin, 2015). Because of the open door policy which is the method by which refugees who fled from the war environment in Syria and are looking for a safe place are hosted in our country with vast opportunities, the practice way of this method, and rules that are not carried out, the record of many refugees could not be kept. (Mercan-Uzun and Bütün, 2016).

Children are inherently attached to and dependent on adults. As a natural consequence of this situation, children are more susceptible to physical injuries, epidemics and emotional trauma (Gürle, 2012). The education lives of young people and children were what were affected the most by the conflicts and civil war in Syria (Seydi, 2014). According to the International Convention on the Rights of the Child, by providing free primary education, all states subject to the treaty accept that every child has the right to receive education (WEB1). Turkey has to take some steps in accordance with international agreements. The inability of refugee children to have sufficient opportunities in the primary education process can be accepted as an indicator of this (Kartal & Başçı, 2014). Not making the education of refugee children compulsory is effective in them keeping away from education (Güneş, 2012). There are not enough opportunities in today's education system for the masses we call immigrants or asylum seekers who were brought up in globalization, our rapidly changing values, communication problems, the problems caused by migration in society, economic problems, cultural conflicts, and who are the most affected ones from these events to become happy, successful individuals who are able to express themselves, who have found themselves and who do not have identity problems (Nalbur-Taşdemir, 2013).

The insufficient attention paid to the services provided to refugees and asylum seekers before the Syrian-centered migration movement and these people remaining in the background is an indication of not being ready for new cases that are faced. Republic of Turkey aims to eliminate the negative effects of Syria-centered migration events. The aim of this study is to contribute to the process of refugee children receiving education in better conditions. In this context, it is predicted that identifying the problems refugee students studying at primary school level face in their education process, and determining what can be done with the perspectives of

students, teachers, parents and administrators in order to eliminate these problems will contribute to making healthier decisions.

1.5. The Significance of the Research

The phenomenon called migration is an undeniable reality of the world countries. People who migrate from their countries for different reasons affect not only their own lives but also the order of the countries they migrate to. At this point, it is important to examine the effects of the currently experienced migration waves from Syria to Turkey. After the migration waves, comes the need for education with the fulfillment of primary needs (food, shelter, health, clothing, etc.). It is inevitable that some problems will occur during the integration of an individual from a different country into the new country. Determining these problems is important for the integration of refugee students into the society. It is aimed to achieve an effective refugee education in our country by identifying and eliminating the problems in the education given to refugee children. This study will contribute to the literature and education policies for refugee students.

The scarcity of studies on the education life of Syrian refugee children at primary school level in the literature and theses suggests the need for this study.

1.6. Purpose of the Research

The purpose of this research is to identify the problems that refugee students encounter in the education process. In accordance with this purpose, answers to the following questions were sought:

1. What are the problems that refugee students face in their education process according to refugee students, parents of students, teachers and primary school administrators?
2. What can be done to solve the problems that refugee students face in the education process according to refugee students, parents of students, teachers and primary school administrators?
3. What are the opinions of refugee students and parents of students regarding the support of teachers and administrators?
4. What are the opinions of refugee students and parents of students on the education they receive in Turkey and in Syria?
5. What are the opinions of teachers and school administrators regarding refugee students?
6. What are the opinions of the teachers regarding the support of school administrators and the opinions of school administrators regarding the support of teachers?

1.7. Assumptions

1. It was assumed that the students included in the study gave correct and sincere answers to the interview forms.
2. It was assumed that the parents included in the study gave correct and sincere answers to the interview forms.
3. It was assumed that the teachers included in the study gave correct and sincere answers to the interview forms.
4. It was assumed that the managers/administrator included in the study gave correct and sincere answers to the interview forms.
5. The interview form is sufficient to determine the opinions of students, parents, teachers and administrators.

1.8. Limitations

1. The data of the research is limited to 18 refugee students, 18 parents of refugee students, 26 teachers and 21 school administrators in the city center of Osmaniye in the 2017-2018 academic year.
2. The data collection tool used in the study is limited to the questions in the semi-structured interview form.

2. METHOD

2.1. Research Model

The qualitative research method was used in this study. The qualitative method is a scientific research method based on non-numerical data, aiming to explore, providing new hypotheses and theories (Johnson & Christensen, 2014). In the qualitative method, the participants participate in the study in their natural environment. The researcher is involved in the process of data collection. They do not have to use scales made by different researchers. Qualitative studies offer a wide variety of data sources (Creswell, 2014). Through qualitative research, the opinions of the participants are presented, the researcher has the opportunity to follow the process in a real environment, working in-depth with a small number of groups is enabled, the data consists of different perspectives and opinions, and these opinions are enabled to be compared (Creswell, 2017).

In this study, phenomenology design, one of the qualitative method types, was used. Phenomenology design, which is the most used qualitative research type, reveals the opinions and perspectives of the participants regarding a phenomenon (Johnson & Christensen, 2014). Phenomenology is the first approach used in qualitative research. This pattern is concerned with what is the consciousness formed in people's experiences, regarding the phenomenon. In-depth interviews are conducted to reveal this consciousness or perspective. The researcher reveals the essence of these experiences from the data he/she collects. Researchers working with phenomenology examine the similarities of the emerging data (Seggie & Bayyurt, 2015). According to Giorgi and Moustakas (1994), philosophy and psychology are based on phenomenology. The essence of the phenomenon is obtained from the opinions about the experiences related to the phenomenon that is the subject of the study through the interviews (Creswell, 2014).

2.2. Study Group

The study group of the research consists of 18 Syrian refugee students who study at 11 primary schools in the province of Osmaniye in the 2017-2018 academic year, 18 Syrian refugee student parents, 26 teachers and 21 administrators that are 83 people in total. The criterion sampling model was used to determine the study group. The following criteria were taken into account in determining the study group:

1. The students participating in the study were chosen from Syrian refugees.
2. All of those Syrian refugee students receive education in the province of Osmaniye.
3. All of the Syrian refugee students selected receive education at primary school level.
4. The criteria for parents participating in the study was determined as refugee parents whose students attend public schools at primary school level.
5. The criterion was that students and parents know the Turkish language enough to answer the questions.
6. The criteria for teachers who participated in the study had Syrian refugee students in their classes.
7. The criterion was that the administrators participating in the study were school administrators having Syrian refugee students in their schools.

According to the demographic data obtained from the student interview forms, the average age of the 18 students interviewed was found to be 10.16. Also, one of these 18 students is in the 2nd grade, 13 of them are in the 3rd grade, and 4 of them are in the 4th grade. The nationality of all the refugee students in Syria. According to the demographic data obtained from the parent interview forms, the average age of the 18 parents interviewed was found to be 34. Also, the nationality of all of the parents in Syria. According to the demographic data obtained from teacher interview forms, the average age of 26 teachers interviewed was found to be 41.92. Also, 6 of 26 teachers teach in 1st grade, 7 in 2nd grade, 7 in 3rd grade and 6 in 4th grade. The average number of Syrian refugee students in teachers' classes was found to be 6.69. According to the demographic data obtained from the administrator interview forms, the average age of 21 school administrators interviewed was found to be 42.61. In addition, 7 of the school administrators are principals and 14 are vice principals. The average of Syrian refugee students that school administrators care for was found to be 77.23.

2.3. Data Collection Tools

4 types of measurement tools were used in collecting research data. They are noted below.

1. Student Interview Form
2. Parent Interview form
3. Teacher Interview Form
4. Administrator Interview Form

Student Interview Form is a semi-structured interview tool developed by the practitioner in order to determine the problems that refugee students encounter in the education process. While preparing the interview forms, care was taken to ensure that the questions were open-ended, understandable, simple and clear, not directing the participant, and conforming with opinion measurement principles. Interview forms were applied to students who could speak Turkish. The answers given by the participants were approved by reading them again. After the interview form is prepared by the researcher, it is presented to an expert who knows the subject of the study for opinion. The expert examines the forms without participating in the research and provides guidance within the scope of grammar, subject relevance or principle of clarity (Glesne, 2013). While preparing this form, necessary arrangements were made by taking expert opinion. Form consists of four questions. The form is presented in Annex-2.

Parent Interview Form is a semi-structured interview tool developed by the practitioner in order to determine the problems that parents of refugee students encounter in the education process. While preparing the interview forms, care was taken to ensure that the questions were open-ended, understandable, simple and clear, not directing the participant, and conforming with opinion measurement principles. Interview forms were applied to parents who could speak Turkish. The answers given by the participants were approved by reading them again. After the interview form is prepared by the researcher, it is presented to an expert who knows the subject of the study for opinion. The expert examines the forms without participating in the research and provides guidance within the scope of grammar, subject relevance or principle of clarity (Glesne, 2013). While preparing this form, necessary arrangements were made by taking expert opinion. The form is presented in Annex-3.

Teacher Interview Form is a semi-structured interview tool developed by the practitioner in order to determine the problems that teachers of refugee students encounter in the education process. While preparing the interview forms, care was taken to ensure that the questions were open-ended, understandable, simple and clear, not directing the participant, and conforming with opinion measurement principles. After the interview form is prepared by the researcher, it is presented to an expert who knows the subject of the study for opinion. The expert examines the forms without participating in the research and provides guidance within the scope of grammar, subject relevance or principle of clarity (Glesne, 2013). While preparing this form, necessary arrangements were made by taking expert opinion. The form is presented in Annex-4.

Administrator Interview Form is a semi-structured interview tool developed by the practitioner in order to determine the problems that administrators who have refugee students in their schools encounter in the education process. While preparing the interview forms, care was taken to ensure that the questions were open-ended, understandable, simple and clear, not directing the participant, and conforming with opinion measurement principles. After the interview form is prepared by the researcher, it is presented to an expert who knows the subject of the study for opinion. The expert examines the forms without participating in the research and provides guidance within the scope of grammar, subject relevance or principle of clarity (Glesne, 2013). While preparing this form, necessary arrangements were made by taking expert opinion. The form is presented in Annex-5.

2.4. The Process of Data Collection

Necessary permissions were obtained from the Osmaniye Directorate of National Education for the implementation of the data collection tools used in the study in primary schools affiliated to the Osmaniye Provincial Directorate of National Education in the 2017-2018 academic year. The permission of the relevant research is provided in Annex-1. In the application process, student, parent, teacher and administrator interview

forms prepared were applied to the participants selected with the criterion sampling model. The interviews lasted approximately 30 minutes. All applications were completed within 2 weeks. The interviews were held at the date and time determined with the participants. During the interviews, it was emphasized to students, teachers, parents and administrators that the answers being correct and sincere was crucial for the research. In addition, it was stated that the answers given by students, parents, teachers and administrators would be confidential and they contributed to a scientific study. All interviews were done face to face. The interviews were recorded without changing the answers given by the researcher to the relevant forms. These forms were then analyzed.

2.5. Data Analysis

In this study, where data were collected using the interview technique, descriptive analysis and content analysis were performed for the analysis of the data, and the findings were presented with their frequencies in the relevant places. The purpose of descriptive analysis is to systematically interpret and present the data obtained by interview or observation technique. The data are classified and interpreted, taking into account the predetermined themes. Comparisons are made with cause-effect relationship (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008).

Content analysis is to obtain concepts and relationships from the findings of the study conducted towards the goal we want to achieve. Undiscovered concepts and themes are achieved thanks to content analysis, which makes a deeper examination than descriptive analysis. Content analysis is based on a stepwise working system. In the first step, concepts are obtained from data. Secondly, concepts are systematized in a logical way and appropriate themes are created accordingly. Content analysis was carried out in 4 stages. First, the data obtained from the interview were coded. Secondly, the common codes were combined, and the themes were achieved. In the third stage, the codes and themes were systematized. Finally, the findings obtained were interpreted (Yıldırım & Şimşek, 2008). In the coding process, the data is read in detail and the codes are obtained from the raw data. Considering the common aspects of the codes, they are combined, and the themes are achieved. Then, the themes are interpreted, and the result is achieved (Creswell, 2017).

The validity and reliability of the data collected with qualitative data collection tools were examined. The peer assessment strategy was used for the accuracy of expression and validity of the findings obtained from the student interview form, parent interview form, teacher interview form and manager interview form. Peer assessment is ensured to be included in the study with the comments of the expert who has information about the project or study, thus the validity is increased. For the reliability of the findings, the analyzes were controlled, the defined codes were reviewed and their accuracies were compared, and the compatibility between the coders was examined (Creswell, 2014).

3. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

3.1.1. Results Regarding the First Sub-Purpose

As a result of the analysis of the findings obtained regarding the first sub-purpose, which investigates the problems that refugee students face in the education process according to the refugee students, parents of students, teachers and primary school administrators, the students made statements within the scope of the sub-themes of aggressive behavior and exclusion. In this case, it is seen that refugee students studying in primary schools are not accepted by Turkish students. It can be said that refugee students experience peer bullying during their education. In the data obtained from the interview forms of some students, it was seen that the refugee students were exposed to peer bullying not only from Turkish students but also from other refugee students.

According to the parents of refugee students, subthemes of not having problems, aggressive behavior, teacher pressure, language problem and exclusion, with frequency order, were created in the theme of problems related to the problems faced by refugee students in the education process. Parents answered the most under the sub-theme "no problem." Parents, according to the problems they stated, showed similarities with the students with the answers they gave in the subthemes of aggressive behavior and exclusion. It can be said that the fact that most of the parents fall into the sub-theme of no problem is related to the fact that they do not take great interest in school. Some parents stated that refugee students were oppressed by teachers.

According to the teachers of the refugee students, according to the data of the problems encountered by the refugee students in the education process, subthemes of communication-adaptation problem, aggressive behavior, psychological problems, absenteeism problem, exclusion problem and financial problems, by the order of frequency, were created. The sub-theme of communication-adaptation problem was the most stated sub-theme by teachers. Teachers have similar statements with parents in terms of the problems they stated regarding communication-adaptation, and with students in terms of aggressive behavior and the exclusion problem.

According to the school administrators in the schools where the refugee students study, the subthemes of communication-adaptation problem, aggressive behavior, psychological problems and academic deficiency, by the order of frequency, were created in the theme of problems related to the problems that refugee students face in the education process. The sub-theme of communication-adaptation problem was the most stated sub-theme by administrators. Administrators made similar statements with the students, parents and teachers in the sub-theme of communication-adaptation problem, and with the teachers in the sub-theme of psychological problems.

Regarding these results, findings that refugee students are exposed to discrimination, have difficulties in language and self-expression, are ridiculed and excluded by others, have difficulties in language learning and adaptation since Turkish is not spoken at home in the study of Nar (2008) titled "The Effects of Migration on Education and Education Management" coincide with the results of this study. Findings that children experience problems in the process of adapting to school, have difficulties in making friends, have communication problems, and their school achievement is lower than other children, in Han (2013)'s thesis titled "Adaptation Problems Faced by Children of Migrant Families in Education" coincide with the results of this study. According to the study titled "Teachers' views on the problems faced by Syrian refugee children in preschool education institutions" conducted by Mercan-Uzun and Bütün (2016), the findings that children have language and communication problems, they are unable to socialize as a result of that, and that they have problems in terms of basic needs such as nutrition, shelter and cleaning coincide with the results of this study. According to the study prepared by Levent and Çayak (2017), titled "Opinions of School Administrators on the Education of Syrian Students in Turkey," the findings regarding the fact that communication problems about refugee students occur have significant similarities with the findings of this thesis study. According to the research prepared by Topsakal, Merey and Keçe (2013) titled "A qualitative study on the education right and problems of children of immigrant families," its findings that children experience cultural conflicts and have problems in adjusting to school coincide with the findings of this study.

3.1.2. Results Regarding the Second Sub-Purpose

According to refugee students, parents of students, teachers and primary school administrators, as a result of the analysis of the findings obtained regarding the second sub-purpose of investigating what can be done to solve the problems faced by refugee students in the education process, sub-themes of positive communication/behavior expectation, not expressing suggestions, teacher assistance expectations, solving the problem on their own, moving away and wishing to die, by the order of frequency of students' answers were formed. The sub-theme of positive communication/behavior expectation was the most expressed solution suggestion. It was seen when the solution suggestions of the students were examined that peer bullying was asked to be eliminated by their friends. Some students, by approaching indirect solutions rather than doing it by themselves, asked their teachers to solve the problems. In this case, it can be said that these students seek support for themselves in the school environment. In a different way, in the case of a student, there was the expression of wishing to die as a solution to the problems. It can be said that this student has severe psychological pressure.

The theme of solutions for the solutions to the problems faced by refugee students in the education process includes sub-themes of language and notion education suggestion for the student, not giving suggestion, language and notion education suggestion for the parents, summer course suggestion and attention expectation by the frequency order of the parents. The sub-theme of language and notion education suggestion for the student was the sub-theme most expressed by the parents in the theme of solutions. While parents focused more on the sub-theme of no problem in the theme of problems, they made suggestions about language in the theme of

solutions. Some parents wanted to support the educational activities of their children by asking for language and notion education not only for the students but also for themselves.

In the study by Erdem (2017) titled "The educational problems of classroom teachers with refugee students in their class and their suggestions on solutions," the findings regarding the fact that a language problem is experienced and the teachers think language education should be provided before school coincide with the results of this study. In the research titled "Teachers' Views on the Education of Syrian Refugees" by Kardeş and Akman (2018), the findings that refugee students have problems in learning languages and adapting to school, and that preschool education is necessary to overcome these problems coincide with the findings of this study. According to the article titled by Sakız (2016) "Immigrant children and school cultures: An integration proposal," the findings of providing education to immigrant children in a separate school coincide with the findings of this study.

3.1.3. Results Regarding the Third Sub-Purpose

Supportive attitude and educational support sub-themes were the sub-themes related to the situation of receiving equal attention from the students and the most attention from the teacher and the administration. There are no students who expressed negative expressions about the state of being cared by the teacher and the administration. Students are very contented with the attention of teachers and administrators who prevent peer bullying in the school environment with a supportive attitude. Some students have received support from the teacher and the administration concerning financial difficulties.

The sub-themes of effective parent communication, academic interest, indifferent, positive response and general support belief, by the order of frequency, were created in the theme of the perception of support regarding the state of getting attention from the teacher or administration in problems experienced according to the parents of refugee students. Effective parent communication sub-theme has been the most expressed one by parents. The indifference sub-theme regarding the perception of support may indicate that parents might have created a negative perception for teachers and administrators.

3.1.4. Results Regarding the Fourth Sub-Purpose

The sub-themes of satisfaction in Turkey, satisfaction in Syria, and equal satisfaction were created in the analysis of the findings regarding the sub-purpose investigating the opinions of refugee students and parents of students concerning the education they receive in Turkey and Syria. Most of the students replied in the sub-theme of satisfaction in Turkey. In this case, it was revealed that refugee students receiving education in primary schools in Turkey are more satisfied with the education system and school environment of Turkey in comparison with Syria. Some students, on the other hand, have never been in the educational environment in Syria. In addition, some students stated that the education processes and school environments of the two countries were equal.

The sub-theme of satisfaction in Turkey was the one expressed the most by parents. Parents stated that they were more satisfied in Turkey than Syria in terms of facilities and academic qualifications offered by the education system and the school environment in Turkey. Parents made similar statements with their students in the theme of satisfaction perception regarding countries.

3.1.5. Results for the Fifth Sub-Purpose

In the analysis of the findings obtained regarding the sub-purpose investigating the opinions of teachers and school administrators about refugee students, according to the data of teachers' feelings regarding having refugee students in their classrooms, the sub-themes of positive perception and feeling discomfort, by the order of frequency, were formed in the theme of perception regarding the refugee student. Positive perception sub-theme was the most expressed sub-theme by teachers. It can be said that teachers' perceptions of refugee students are at a positive level.

Regarding the perceptions of administrators on having refugee students in their schools, the sub-themes of positive perception and feeling discomfort, by the order of frequency, were created in the theme of perception of the refugee student. Positive perception sub-theme was the most expressed sub-theme by the administrators. Administrators' perceptions of refugee students are positive. Administrators and teachers made similar statements in this regard.

According to the thesis titled "Researching the experiences of education stakeholders in a public school in Mamak, regarding refugee education" by Erçakır-Kozan (2019) regarding this result, the findings regarding communication problems with refugee students and their parents, teachers experiencing problems arising from the large number of refugee students and wanting to increase their professional development, educators having positive attitudes towards refugee students, and refugee families' satisfaction with the education they have accessed coincide with the results of this study.

3.1.6. Results for Sixth Sub-Purpose

In the analysis of the findings obtained regarding the sub-purpose investigating the opinions of the teachers regarding the support of school administrators and school administrators regarding the support of teachers, the sub-themes of getting support from the administrator and not being able to get support from the administrator, by the order of frequency, were created in the theme of support between the teacher and the administrator regarding the status of teachers of refugee students in finding support from the school administrators in the face of problems experienced. The sub-theme of getting support from the administrator was the most expressed sub-theme by the teachers. In this case, teachers work on the problems of refugee students in cooperation with the administration.

According to the school administrators in the schools where the refugee students are studying, sub-themes of getting support from the teacher and not being able to get support from the teacher, by the order of frequency, were created in the theme of support between the teacher and the administrator regarding the status of administrators in finding support from the teachers in the face of problems. The sub-theme "I can get support from the teacher" was the most expressed sub-theme by the administrators. Teachers and administrators made statements supporting each other in the theme of support between the teacher and the administrator and stated that the relations between the administrators and the teachers in their schools were positive.

3.2. Suggestions

1. The Ministry of National Education should open support courses for students and parents in order to solve the language problem regarding the adaptation of refugee students and their families to Turkey.
2. In order for refugee children and their families to benefit fully from the guiding in education, in-service training should be provided to administrators and teachers, families and students should be informed and made aware of this subject.
3. Adaptation programs specific to refugee families and their children should be organized and implemented. Help should be sought from the Guidance Research Center (GRC), Provincial Directorate of Family and Social Policies and universities on this subject.
4. Studies should be conducted in other provincial examples regarding the problems of refugee students and the results obtained by comparing with this study should be generalized.
5. In order for refugee students and other students to adapt to each other, teachers and administrators should receive orientation training and arrange the practices for children.

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